

Interpolating Discrete Functions through Riemann-Liouville Fractional Integrals

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April 20, 2026

Abstract

A method to find an analytic function passing through any countable set of points is provided. A proof of analyticity is also provided. This method is based on the fact that the formula

$$f(n) = \left[\frac{d^n}{dt^n} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} f(k) \frac{t^k}{k!} \right]_{t=0},$$

can be extended using the Riemann-Liouville fractional derivative ${}_{\xi}D_t^z$ (defined in Section 1), enabling to evaluate the derivative of any order $z \in \mathbb{C}$,

$$f(z) = \left[{}_{\xi}D_t^z \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} f(k) \frac{t^k}{k!} \right]_{t=0}.$$

This provides a simple formula to interpolate an arbitrary set of points of the form $(n, f(n))$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Generalizations are provided to interpolate any countable set of points, given appropriate conditions.

1 Introduction

This paper aims to provide an additional application of the fractional calculus in the context of the generation of an analytic function passing through an arbitrary set of points. We are well aware of the fact that it is possible in the field of complex analysis to find such a function as the product between a function with prescribed zeros and a function with prescribed poles (by the Weierstrass and Mittag-Leffler theorems [1, 2], respectively). However, this latter method can be arbitrarily complicated depending on the number of points in the set and the series convergence associated with it. On the other hand, the method provided here only involves the application of one integral transform and is arguably more straightforward.

The Riemann-Liouville fractional integral of an analytic function f is defined as

$$({}_{\xi}J_t^{\alpha} f)(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{\xi}^t (t - \tau)^{\alpha-1} f(\tau) d\tau, \quad (1)$$

where $\alpha \in \mathbb{C}$, α is the order of the operator, and $t \in (\xi, +\infty)$, $\xi \in \mathbb{R}$. Hence, the Riemann-Liouville fractional derivative is defined as the ordinary derivative of the fractional integral,

$$({}_{\xi}D_t^{n-\alpha} f)(t) = \frac{d^n}{dt^n} ({}_{\xi}J_t^{\alpha} f)(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \frac{d^n}{dt^n} \int_{\xi}^t (t - \tau)^{\alpha-1} f(\tau) d\tau, \quad (2)$$

where $0 \leq n \in \mathbb{N}_0$, $0 \leq \operatorname{Re}\{\alpha\} \leq n$, and $n - \alpha$ is the order of the operator [3–5]. The constraints given here are assumed to stand for every instance of the operator from now on.

For the purpose of the method provided in the next section, it is important to prove various properties of these operators.

Theorem 1.1. *The result of the RL fractional derivative does not change by setting $\alpha \rightarrow \alpha - k$ and $n \rightarrow n - k$, so long as $\alpha - k > 0$.*

Proof. Using the Leibniz integral rule k times,

$$\begin{aligned}
&({}_\xi D_t^{n-\alpha} f)(t) \\
&= \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \frac{d^n}{dt^n} \int_\xi^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} f(\tau) d\tau \\
&= \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \frac{d^{n-1}}{dt^{n-1}} \left[\cancel{(t-t)^{\alpha-1} f(t) \frac{dt}{dt}} + \cancel{(t-\xi)^{\alpha-1} f(\xi) \frac{d\xi}{dt}} + \int_\xi^t \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} f(\tau) d\tau \right] \\
&= \dots \\
&= \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{\Gamma(\alpha-k)} \frac{d^{n-k}}{dt^{n-k}} \left[\cancel{(t-t)^{\alpha-k} f(t) \frac{dt}{dt}} + \cancel{(t-\xi)^{\alpha-k} f(\xi) \frac{d\xi}{dt}} + \int_\xi^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-k-1} f(\tau) d\tau \right] \\
&= \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha-k)} \frac{d^{n-k}}{dt^{n-k}} \int_\xi^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-k-1} f(\tau) d\tau,
\end{aligned}$$

where the cancellings can be done as $\text{Re}\{\alpha\} - k > 0$ by hypothesis. \square

Property 1.2. *Given that $n - \alpha \in \mathbb{N}$, then*

$$({}_\xi D_t^{n-\alpha} f)(t) = \frac{d^{n-\alpha} f}{dt^{n-\alpha}}. \quad (3)$$

Proof. The following proof is due to Ortigueira et al. [6] and is reproposed here for clarity. The power function defined as $(t-\tau)_+^\alpha$ (equal to $(t-\tau)^\alpha$ when $t > \tau$, and 0 otherwise) has a Laurent series expansion around a negative integer $-n$ [7]

$$(t-\tau)_+^\alpha = \frac{(-1)^{n-1} \delta^{(n-1)}(t-\tau)}{(n-1)!(\alpha-n)} + (t-\tau)^{-n} + (\alpha+n)(t-\tau)^{-n} \ln(t-\tau) + \dots \quad (4)$$

Dividing by the gamma function and taking the limit $\alpha \rightarrow -n$, all the analytic terms go to zero because of the poles of the gamma function, as in

$$\lim_{\alpha \rightarrow -n} \frac{(t-\tau)_+^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} = \frac{(-1)^{n-1} \delta^{(n-1)}(t-\tau)}{(n-1)!(\alpha-n)\Gamma(\alpha+1)} + \frac{(t-\tau)^{-n}}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} + \dots = \delta^{(n-1)}(t-\tau). \quad (5)$$

Showing that the kernel of the RL fractional integral tends to the identity as the order $\alpha \rightarrow 0$. Because of Theorem 1.1, any combination of n and α such that $n - \alpha = m \in \mathbb{N}$ will have $({}_x D_t^{n-\alpha} f)(t) = \frac{d^m f}{dt^m}$ as desired. \square

Theorem 1.3. *The RL derivative evaluated at some constant $t > \xi$, $({}_x D_t^{n-\alpha} f)(t)$ is an analytic function with respect to α , in the region $0 \leq \text{Re}\{\alpha\} \leq n$.*

Proof. Starting with the definition, and integrating by parts n times,

$$\begin{aligned}
&({}_\xi D_t^{n-\alpha} f)(t) \\
&= \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \frac{d^n}{dt^n} \int_\xi^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} f(\tau) d\tau \\
&= \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \frac{d^n}{dt^n} \left[-\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{\Gamma(\alpha+k)} (t-\tau)^{\alpha+k-1} f^{(k-1)}(\tau) + \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{\Gamma(\alpha+n)} \int (t-\tau)^{\alpha+n-1} f^{(n)}(\tau) d\tau \right]_\xi^t \\
&= \frac{d^n}{dt^n} \left[\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(t-\xi)^{\alpha+k-1}}{\Gamma(\alpha+k)} f^{(k-1)}(\xi) + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+n)} \int_\xi^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha+n-1} f^{(n)}(\tau) d\tau \right] \\
&= \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(t-\xi)^{\alpha+k-n-1}}{\Gamma(\alpha+k-n)} f^{(k-1)}(\xi) + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_\xi^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} f^{(n)}(\tau) d\tau.
\end{aligned}$$

The terms of the sum are all analytic, as the inverse of the gamma function is entire and so is the exponential. Because $\text{Re}\{\alpha\} \geq 0$ and f is analytic, the integral converges absolutely so that the whole expression is analytic with respect to α (in the case of equality this is ensured by Property 1.2). It follows (by the constraints given in Eq. 2 and Property 1.2) that the region of analyticity is $0 \leq \text{Re}\{\alpha\} \leq n$, where the inclusion of the extremes is still given by Property 1.2. \square

Lemma 1.4. *The RL derivative evaluated at some constant $t > \xi$, $({}_1 D_t^z f)(t)$, is unique and analytic with respect to z no matter the choice of α and n so long as $\text{Re}\{\alpha\} \leq n$ and $z = n - \alpha$.*

Proof. Say a derivative is evaluated with some fixed integer n , $({}_1 D_t^{n-\alpha} f)(t)$, and with another integer $m > n$, $({}_2 D_t^{m-\beta} f)(t)$. By Theorem 1.1 if $m - \beta = n - \alpha$, that is, the derivatives have the same order, then the two derivatives are equal. Now let $z = n - \alpha = m - \beta$ be the order of the derivative. The region of analyticity of $({}_1 D_t^z f)(t)$ is $0 \leq \text{Re}\{z\} \leq n$, whereas that of $({}_2 D_t^z f)(t)$ is $0 \leq \text{Re}\{z\} \leq m$, by Theorem 1.3. Because the two are equal in the region $0 \leq \text{Re}\{z\} \leq n$, then $({}_2 D_t^z f)(t)$ is the analytic continuation of $({}_1 D_t^z f)(t)$ with respect to the order of the derivative, by the uniqueness of analytic continuation [8]. This implies the existence of an analytic function of z in the positive half plane $({}_1 D_t^z f)(t)$, that continues all other functions no matter the choice of n . \square

Lemma 1.5. *The derivative $({}_1 D_t^z f)(t)$ is equal to the analytic continuation of $({}_1 J_t^{z^*} f)(t)$ in z^* 's negative half plane, where $z = -z^*$ and evaluated at a constant $t > \xi$.*

Proof. By direct calculation of the derivative of order $n - \text{Re}\{\alpha\} < 0$ (still $n \in \mathbb{N}$),

$$\begin{aligned}
({}_1 D_t^{n-\alpha} f)(t) &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \frac{d^n}{dt^n} \int_\xi^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} f(\tau) d\tau \\
&= \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha-n)} \int_\xi^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-n-1} f(\tau) d\tau = ({}_1 J_t^{\alpha-n} f)(t),
\end{aligned}$$

where all the non-integral terms are zero as in the working provided in Theorem 1.1. By uniqueness of analytic continuation [8], the RHS is the analytic continuation of the LHS. \square

Note that the RL integral can converge for $0 > \alpha \in \mathbb{Z}$ and be different to its corresponding derivative. This is not a problem, since the lemma refers to the analytic continuation of the integral and hence one should rather evaluate $\lim_{\alpha \rightarrow -n} ({}_1 J_t^\alpha f)(t)$ and this will indeed be equal to the corresponding derivative $({}_1 D_t^{-\alpha} f)(t)$. This last lemma will be useful for the application of the method, that is exemplified in Appendix A.

Example of Fractional Derivative Interpolation

Figure 1: Plots of interpolated graphs using Eq. (8). The plotted functions have as generatrix and parameter ξ , respectively, a) $\frac{1}{x+1}$, $\xi = -1$, b) $\sum_{k=0}^{10} k e^k \frac{x^k}{k!}$, $\xi = -1.03$, c) $\sum_{k=0}^{10} \frac{1}{k+1} \frac{x^k}{k!}$, $\xi = -5$, d) $\sum_{k=0}^4 \frac{x^k}{k!}$, $\xi = -5$. Notice in plot c) a little deviation from the function $\frac{1}{1+x}$ in the tail. This artifact is caused by the fact that the generatrix function is not an infinite sum, and the function generated crosses 0 at every other integer greater than 10. Also notice in plot d) the sum of the first 5 terms of the expansion of the exponential; the truncation of the series is the reason why the function is 0 for integers greater than 4.

2 Method

The objective is to produce an analytic function passing through a set of points of the form $(n, f(n)) \forall n \in \mathbb{N}$. First, notice how taking the n^{th} derivative of the Maclaurin series below and evaluating it at 0 one gets back the n^{th} coefficient,

$$f(n) = \left[\frac{d^n}{dt^n} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} f(k) \frac{t^k}{k!} \right]_{t=0}, \quad (6)$$

where $f : \mathbb{C} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$, but the only known points of f are $k \in \mathbb{N}$. This formula is the key to the solution, as replacing the derivative operator with the Riemann-Liouville fractional derivative operator will enable to obtain an analytic function passing through all points $(n, f(n)) \forall n \in \mathbb{N}$. Please note that we assume convergence of the series on some disk of the complex plane, and this constrains the possible values that $f(n)$ can take. This assumption can be relaxed given the appropriate conditions laid out in the next section.

Modifying Eq. (6), f can be extended by stating

$$f(z) = \left[{}_{\xi} D_t^z \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} f(k) \frac{t^k}{k!} \right]_{t=0}, \quad (7)$$

where $0 \leq \text{Re}\{z\}$, $0 > \xi \in \mathbb{R}$. This function indeed interpolates the points $(n, f(n))$ as if $z = n \in \mathbb{N}$, Property 1.2 gives $[{}_{\xi} D_t^z g]_{t=0} = [d^n g / dt^n]_{t=0} = f(n)$. Function $f : \mathbb{C} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ is analytic because of Lemma 1.4. Please note that this expression only requires one to know the values of f at positive integer values of k to reconstruct an analytic version of f itself.

Effect of Changing the Lower Limit of Integration

Figure 2: Different plots for the functions obtained from the generatrix $\sum_{k=0}^{20} p_k \frac{x^k}{k!}$, where p_k is the k^{th} prime, for values a) $\xi = -2$, b) $\xi = -6$, c) $\xi = -9$, d) $\xi = -12$.

In general, Eq. 7 can be written as

$$f(z) = [\xi D_t^z g]_{t=0}, \quad (8)$$

where $g : \mathbb{C} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ is analytic at 0. In the context of the latter equation, function g from now on will be referred to as the generatrix function of f . This method provides a way of finding a function passing through a given set of points with the restriction that, for now, they are of the form $(n, y_n) \forall n \in \mathbb{N}$, and that the associated generatrix function g converges in some disc of the complex plane. This means that say g converges in a disc $\|z\| < r$, then $\|\xi\| < r$. Note that once this interpolating function is found, there is a free parameter ξ whose value will not influence the fact that, at positive integers, the function is equal to the chosen points. In fact, one could make $\xi = \xi(z)$ an analytic function, even though this could prevent analyticity of f .

In Fig. 1 it is possible to see some plots derived from the use of this method along with their associated generatrix functions. As it is possible to see, the plots cross all the points desired. For instance, plot d) perfectly shows how the generated function has $f(x) = 1$ for integer x from 0 to 4, and has $f(x) = 0$ for every other positive integer value. Also an illustration of how the parameter ξ alters the interpolation is provided in Fig. 2 where the different functions are generated from the same generatrix with different values of ξ . Notice how changing ξ does not affect the fact that the generated function passes through the desired points. In the Appendix A it is possible to find an example related to the Gamma function.

3 Generalizations

A method for finding an analytic version for a function f given points $(n, f(n)) \forall n \in \mathbb{N}$ with an associated converging g has been found. Now it is necessary to extend this method to any set of points of the form $(a_n, f(a_n)) \forall n \in \mathbb{N}$ and points in a space of arbitrary dimension.

Assume for now that the set of points $(n, f(n))$ with an associated generatrix $g(z) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} f(k) \frac{z^k}{k!}$ does not converge in any disc. Then, if it is possible to define $g_l = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} l(f(k)) \frac{z^k}{k!}$ where $l: \mathbb{C} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ is analytic and g_l converges in an arbitrary disc, then it is possible to find f by saying

$$f(z) = l^{-1} \{ [\xi D_t^z g_l]_{t=0} \}. \quad (9)$$

Now, given a set of points of the form $(a_n, f(a_n)) \forall n \in \mathbb{N}$ with an associated converging g and an analytic map $m: \mathbb{C} \rightarrow \mathbb{C} \mid m(n) = a_n \forall n \in \mathbb{N}$. Then,

$$f_{\mathbb{N}}(z) = \left[\xi D_t^z \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} f(a_k) \frac{t^k}{k!} \right]_{t=0}, \quad (10)$$

and

$$f(z) = f_{\mathbb{N}}(m^{-1}(z)). \quad (11)$$

In this way one can say,

$$f(z) = \left[\xi D_t^{m^{-1}(z)} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} f(a_k) \frac{t^k}{k!} \right]_{t=0}. \quad (12)$$

It is easy to check that f passes through points $(a_n, f(a_n))$. Note that if m is not injective, then f is a multivalued function. Please note that one can always resort to the method given in the previous section to construct m .

To generalize the definition for a space of arbitrary dimension first define the partial fractional order Riemann-Liouville derivative,

$$(\xi P_{t_1}^x f)(t_1, t_2, \dots, t_q) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \frac{\partial^n}{\partial t_1^n} \int_{\xi}^{t_1} (t_1 - \tau_1)^{\alpha-1} f(\tau_1, t_2, \dots, t_q) d\tau_1. \quad (13)$$

Now, say $f: \mathbb{C}^q \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ and $f = f(t_1, t_2, \dots, t_q)$, then the following is an identity,

$$f(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_q) = \left[\frac{\partial^{n_1}}{\partial t_1^{n_1}} \frac{\partial^{n_2}}{\partial t_2^{n_2}} \dots \frac{\partial^{n_q}}{\partial t_q^{n_q}} \sum_{k_1=0}^{\infty} \sum_{k_2=0}^{\infty} \dots \sum_{k_q=0}^{\infty} f(k_1, k_2, \dots, k_q) \frac{t_1^{k_1} t_2^{k_2} \dots t_q^{k_q}}{k_1! k_2! \dots k_q!} \right]_{t_1=0, \dots, t_q=0}.$$

A more rigorous theoretical backbone should have been given, but the following is provided as an illustration of possible generalizations that can be done. Hence, replacing the partial differential it is possible to conclude that,

$$f(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_q) = \left[\xi P_{t_1}^{x_1} \xi P_{t_2}^{x_2} \dots \xi P_{t_q}^{x_q} \sum_{k_1=0}^{\infty} \sum_{k_2=0}^{\infty} \dots \sum_{k_q=0}^{\infty} f(k_1, k_2, \dots, k_q) \frac{t_1^{k_1} t_2^{k_2} \dots t_q^{k_q}}{k_1! k_2! \dots k_q!} \right]_{t_1=0, \dots, t_q=0}.$$

At this point it is possible to perform the same generalization as above mapping the points from the form $(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_q, f(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_q)) \forall n_1, n_2, \dots, n_q \in \mathbb{N}$ to a set of points where the first coordinates have the relaxed constraint $(c_{n_1}, c_{n_2}, \dots, c_{n_q}, f(c_{n_1}, c_{n_2}, \dots, c_{n_q})) \forall c_{n_1}, c_{n_2}, \dots, c_{n_q} \in \mathbb{C}$.

4 Conclusions

A systematic method to obtain the interpolation of any discrete function has been provided. This method produces an analytic function that interpolates any countable set of points, provided that we are able to find maps that converge on some region of the complex plane.

Generalizations to the method have also been provided, to enable the interpolation of n -dimensional functions, and to adapt to any infinitely countable set of points. A theoretical backbone was provided for the core method, but further research is required to legitimize the n -dimensional interpolation that has been proposed in the last section. Further research is also needed to examine convergence properties of the integrals and to find the limitations on the existence of the map l provided in Section 3.

Such generalizations are important to provide flexibility to the method, in order to facilitate the development of eventual applications that it may find.

A Example

Interpolating Γ First one wishes to find a function whose derivative gives discrete points from the gamma function. Consider

$$g(t) = \frac{1}{1-t} \quad \text{as} \quad \left. \frac{d^n g}{dt^n} \right|_{t=0} = n!.$$

One wishes to prove that, for some ξ , the following holds,

$$\Gamma(z+1) = \left[\xi D_t^z \frac{1}{1-t} \right]_{t=0}. \quad (14)$$

So starting from the equation for g , and evaluating at $t=0$ as prescribed by Eq. 8

$$\left[\xi J_t^z \frac{1}{1-t} \right]_{t=0} = \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(z)} \int_{\xi}^t (t-\tau)^{z-1} \frac{1}{1-\tau} d\tau \right]_{t=0} = \frac{1}{\Gamma(z)} \int_{\xi}^0 (-\tau)^{z-1} \frac{1}{1-\tau} d\tau.$$

Now choose $\xi \rightarrow -\infty$ and $\tau = -\frac{u}{1-u}$, so that $\frac{d\tau}{du} = -\frac{1}{(1-u)^2}$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \left[\xi J_t^z \frac{1}{1-t} \right]_{t=0} &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(z)} \int_1^0 \left(\frac{u}{1-u} \right)^{z-1} \left(1 + \frac{u}{1-u} \right)^{-1} \left(-\frac{1}{(1-u)^2} \right) du \\ &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(z)} \int_0^1 u^{z-1} (1-u)^{-z} du. \end{aligned}$$

Now, being aware that this integral converges only for $0 < \|z\| < 1$, we evaluate its result and consider its analytic continuation. According to Lemma 1.5 this analytic continuation will be the result of the corresponding RL fractional derivative. So, recognizing the integral representation of the Beta function,

$$= \frac{1}{\Gamma(z)} B(z, -z+1) = \frac{\Gamma(z)\Gamma(-z+1)}{\Gamma(z)\Gamma(1)} = \Gamma(-z+1).$$

So because in the disk $0 < \|z\| < 1$,

$$\left[-\infty J_t^z \frac{1}{1-t} \right]_{t=0} = \Gamma(-z+1),$$

then, by analytic continuation and Lemma 1.5,

$$\left[-\infty D_t^z \frac{1}{1-t} \right]_{t=0} = \Gamma(z+1), \quad (15)$$

as desired.

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